

Developing a patient, public engagement and insight dashboard for the Secure Data Environment programme

A report for the DARE UK Early Adopter PANORAMA Project by Olovus Ltd.

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1. Patient, Public, Engagement and Involvement at the heart of the NHS England Secure Data Environment programme

1.1. Background

The development of a Patient, Public, Engagement and Involvement (PPIE) insight dashboard sits within a wider national shift in how patient and public involvement and engagement is positioned within health data research and digital infrastructure.

From the outset, NHS England's Secure Data Environment programme has taken a deliberate decision to place patient and public involvement at its core, rather than treating it as a parallel or downstream activity. This reflects a recognition that public trust, social licence, and legitimacy are foundational to the long-term success of Secure Data Environments, particularly where data is used without explicit consent for research and population health purposes.

As a result, PPIE within the SDE programme has been comparatively well resourced, both in terms of dedicated funding and senior leadership attention. This has enabled regions not only to deliver engagement activity, but to invest in capability building, shared learning, and the development of more consistent good practice.

A key feature of the SDE approach has been the establishment of a national PPIE community of practice, bringing together practitioners from across regions alongside NHS England colleagues. The community of practice has provided a practical space for shared problem solving, peer challenge, and collective reflection on what builds trust, what damages it, and how to respond when the public's questions become more demanding as programmes scale.

It has also surfaced a stubborn, delivery-level reality; different regions have developed different engagement approaches, tools, and reporting formats. That variation is often appropriate and rooted in local context, but it makes it hard to compare activity, spot gaps, and reuse learning across the programme. Hence, despite significant activity, resulting insights do not always translate into system change and collective wisdom at a rate or effectiveness acceptable to our community. In short, PPIE practice has matured faster than the infrastructure available to record it, aggregate it, and show its value.

The dashboard concept emerged from this frustration to close an operational and strategic gap, improve the efficiency of knowledge transfer and improve matrix working. It is not a response to a lack of

engagement. It is a response to a level of ambition and activity that has outgrown traditional narrative reporting.

1.2. Starting point: Federation creates a trust test, not just a technical challenge

The pan-North federation work sharpened this further. Federation makes visible what has long been true, but easier to overlook when programmes stay local. Public acceptability does not rest on technical assurances alone. It rests on whether people can see that decisions are being taken carefully, consistently, and with meaningful public voice.

The PANORAMA engagement findings show broad support for data use for research and public benefit but also make clear that support becomes conditional when people move from principle to practice and when activity scales across organisations and geographies. People want to know who is involved, whose voices count, how local perspectives are protected, and what happens when concerns are raised. Federation, therefore, introduces a trust test that cannot be met through reassurance and narrative alone. It requires visible, auditable practice.

This creates a dual requirement for the programme. It must both do PPIE well and also show that PPIE working in a way that is credible to both the public and system leaders. These requirements depend on PPIE improving and aligning its system architecture to adhere to the FAIR principles that govern data use.

1.3. The practical problem the programme was facing

Before the dashboard concept emerged, PPIE activity across the SDE landscape was already extensive. Engagement was happening through workshops, advisory groups, deliberative processes, surveys, and local conversations. However, that activity was difficult to see as a coherent whole.

Reporting was fragmented and largely retrospective. Insight was locked into individual reports and slide decks. Demographic information was collected inconsistently, making it hard to assess inclusion or bias. Learning was not easily reusable across programmes or regions and critically there was no simple way to answer basic assurance questions at pace, such as:

- Are we hearing from the same people repeatedly?
- Which communities or geographies are missing?

- What concerns are emerging consistently across different conversations?
- How are those concerns influencing governance and delivery decisions?

This was not a failure of intent or effort. It was a systems problem. PPIE practice had outgrown the infrastructure supporting it and needed to evolve to a state of intentionally coordinated effort with explicit communication pipelines to senior leaders in a near-real-time manner.

2. Reframing PPIE as ‘Transparency Infrastructure’

The insight dashboard concept reframes PPIE reporting as transparency infrastructure. Rather than treating reporting as an administrative afterthought, it positions public consultation as a core enabling function for trust, accountability, and learning. Public trust can be earned by making clearer whose opinions were sought, why, where, when and in what context, and how resultant policy is more inclusive and well designed as a result.

The intention is not surveillance of PPIE activity, nor centralised control of engagement. It is about creating a shared, structured way of seeing what is happening so that judgement, challenge, and improvement are possible. It supports the programme to make transparency demonstrable rather than relying on narrative. Key outputs should be improved consensus-based steering of activity and efforts, and a move away from top-down direction which can lag behind the collective PPIE professional communities, academic and advocacy groups’ own understanding of issues closer to the ground.

Our framing as transparency infrastructure draws on established principles in health data governance. Good practice approaches such as the Five Safes and fair principles emphasise that trust is built through demonstrable process, not aspiration. The dashboard applies that thinking to public involvement itself

The insight platform represents a solution that enhances PPIE impacts via the establishment of common data models, reporting standards and near real-time visualisation. By embedding best data practice from other expert domains, PPIE as a function can demonstrate reciprocity and the ability to model the behaviours that it attempts to engender in the expert groups it informs.

2.1. How the idea emerged in practice

The dashboard did not begin as a formally commissioned product but rather emerged out of relationships formed with other PPIE community practice members and “watercooler” conversations around collective pain points. Early discussions highlighted a recurring question:

Is involvement proactively shaping decisions, or is it mainly being used to socialise decisions already leaning in a particular direction?

Answering that required visibility of timing, reach, and influence, not just a list of activities after the fact.

In parallel, work on transparency and social licence highlighted a gap between what programmes believed they were doing and what could be evidenced externally. When challenged, teams could describe their approach, but could not always demonstrate it consistently and accessibly, especially when asked to show patterns over time or across geographies.

The insight dashboard idea emerged as a response to these pressures. It was conceived as a practical mechanism to bring together activity, insight, and accountability in near real time, rather than as a collection of unconnected retrospective reports.

Observing that information flows to the centre but the value returned to the community is often limited, Dr Dale Kirkwood developed the vision to liberate PPIE data, reduce duplication of effort and build trust through transparency. Ideation and design approaches were born out of consultations for Data Saves Lives and PEDRI Good Practice Standards held in June 2023. Dr Kirkwood was keen to explore how such standards are implemented into practice but shifted his focus to how we measure and hold ourselves and the wider system accountable to their aspirations. This blended his experience from roles in national patient safety space as Co-chair of Quality Improvement at the Royal College of Emergency Medicine and as a Pre-doctoral fellow hosted at Lancashire Teaching Hospitals NHS Foundation Trust Data Science Unit.

Through a series of task and finish groups, Dr Kirkwood and Caroline Latta of the North East and North Cumbria SDE, in collaboration with Amy Darlington (Chair of the NHS SDE PPIE community group) developed a reporting framework covering diversity and inclusion metrics, strategy and planning, and operational data.

The requirements were mapped to PEDRI Good Practice, SATRE and Public Sector Equality Duty requirements to rationalise their inclusion. This work identified that “semi-automation” of diversity data collection would be desirable to improve efficiency and reduce the burden on PPIE professionals and the public. It was identified that real-time data capture could provide sufficient meta-data to engineer an extensive suit of insights from a minimal dataset. Grace Mullins and colleagues from the Yorkshire and Humber SDE were simultaneously working on a common data model and reporting format and this work was later blended into the insight platform.

2.2. From concept to early specification

As thinking progressed it became clear that a traditional reporting dashboard would not be sufficient. A usable system would need to address the full lifecycle of PPIE activity, from planning and data capture through to analysis and outputs.

This led to the articulation of the dashboard as an end-to-end system with four core components:

1. a minimal common dataset without direct identifiers that can be captured consistently across different types of involvement
2. a simple data capture route that fits into real delivery workflows both online and in-person

3. an aggregation and visualisation layer that supports oversight and gap analysis
4. outputs that can be shared both internally and with public audiences without disclosure risk

This approach deliberately avoids over engineering. The working assumption is that good enough, used consistently, is more valuable than perfect but unused.

3. Design principles shaped by practitioner reality

Four principles have guided development so far.

3.1. Co-design with real users

Development is intentionally grounded in practitioner and public user testing, rather than abstract debate. This keeps the work rooted in delivery reality. Public, PPIE professional and leaders are to be involved in design decisions to improve platform functionality and quality.

3.2. Usability before sophistication

The tool must be quick to use and intuitive. If it increases administrative burden or requires specialist skills, it will not be adopted. The specification therefore prioritises a small core dataset and rapid input, with scope to layer additional analysis later.

Privacy and proportionality

Equality and demographic data are essential for understanding inclusion, but they also increase identifiability risk. The design therefore emphasises aggregation, suppression rules, and role-based access, aligned with information governance best practice.

3.3. Symmetrical transparency

The system is designed so that leadership oversight and practitioner views are aligned, rather than operating in parallel. Public-facing outputs should reflect the same underlying data, presented in accessible language and formats.

3.4. How the dashboard supports federation in practice

In the context of pan-North federation, the dashboard functions as part of the trust architecture.

4. Longer-term ambition to expand usability

The Insight dashboard can provide a way to demonstrate that public involvement is happening locally, consistently, and visibly across federated regions. It allows patterns to be seen without erasing local differences. It supports assurance that public concerns are not diluted as decisions scale.

It can also support internal discipline. By making gaps and inconsistencies visible, it enables earlier course correction and more intentional engagement planning, including targeting under-represented voices and making sure that involvement effort is proportionate to risk and impact.

In this sense, the dashboard is not simply a reporting tool. It is an enabling mechanism that supports better decision making, better PPIE practice, and from that, greater public confidence.

Structured PPIE data opens up the possibility of reducing manual analysis burden, improving the timeliness of insight, and enabling learning across programmes and regions. Over time, this could allow practitioners to spend less effort on retrospective reporting and more on reaching under-represented voices and responding to what they hear.

While the immediate focus is on a minimum viable product, the longer-term ambition is more strategic with a view to integrating conversations and qualitative insight production. This would require leveraging emergent ambient voice, real-time transcription, AI inference and analytical capabilities to improve problem identification and insight production. But most critically these technologies will require the development of a shared data infrastructure and reporting practice that is also trusted by professionals as accurate, transparent and able to be scrutinised.

Our work is explicit that automation should support professional judgement, not replace it. There is a recognised risk that tools which remove practitioners from the analysis process can weaken reflective practice. This will need to be actively managed as the system evolves.

5. Next Steps

- The current direction focuses on these near-term priorities.
- Finalising a minimal viable product scope and common definitions
- Confirming the minimal dataset, visual outputs, and governance guardrails.
- Building a capture route that fits real workflows
- Making sure the system integrates with how involvement is delivered.
- Testing with practitioners and public contributors
- Using rapid iteration to identify usability issues, disclosure risks, and unintended consequences.

These steps are intended to keep the work grounded, practical, and aligned with the core purpose of strengthening trust through visible, accountable practice.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

Appendix 1: Adapted PEDRI Good Practice Standards

This infographic explores the relationship of different [PEDRI](#) values to different groups of professionals, acknowledging that the authority, influence and ability to deliver them sit within different collectives. This enables a focus on responsibility. Note “accountable systems” has been added as an additional value in this example.

The impact chain borrows and blends a concept from the Resus Council’s “chain of survival” in life support, stressing the importance of early recognition of a problem (cardiac arrest) and good downstream actions to protect life and quality of life. Each link in the chain needs to be strong to support the desired overall outcome. For PPIE, this translates as strong public trust from transparent consultation, providing a voice that has tangible impacts on policy direction.

Appendix 2: Benefits realisation and metric matrix

Developed by Dr Dale Kirkwood with support from Caroline Latta in August 2024 as part of a Task and Finish Group, established within the NHS SDE Community of Practice, in an attempt to improve reporting transparency and knowledge transfer.

Benefits realisation and metrics matrix													
The rating system of +, ++, +++ is the maximal potential impact of an area being delivered well. For example collecting public EDI data within health won't create diversity but it has a lot of power to demonstrate the systems delivery of successful inclusion and a lack of it													
Objective	Key Item/result	Type of measurement	Reporting responsibility/Autonomy?	Reporting frequency	Values					Legal Requirements			
					PEDR Standards					SAIRE		PSED	Section 251
					Effective Comms	Meaningful Engagement	Data literacy & Training	Diversity & Inclusion	Manual Benefit	Proactive Transparency	Accountability		
1	Develop and deliver a clear strategy with national, regional and local alignment	Yes - in progress - No Checklist (To deliver on the values, accreditation and legal duties) Yes - in progress - No Reports/Presentations in CoP - Self assessment	PPE Leads PPE Leads PPE Leads PPE Leads	Once (annual) Once (annual) Quarterly Quarterly (One per year CoP presentation)	++ ++ ++ +++	++ ++ ++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	++ ++ +++ +++	++ ++ ++ ++	+++ +++ +++ +++	++ ++ ++ +++	
2	Impact Reports	Published Centrally - News	PPE Lead/Comms	Quarterly (Each region presents to the CoP annual)	+++ +++ +++ +++								
3	Involving diverse perspectives within the programme	Quantitative - Contracts/Hours/meeting dates - These would be linked to the EDI data Need a clear process and DMA and link to the Equality Act (2010) + PSED. Need be clear where and how it is being used. 4 part year code AB213-	Semi-automated Semi-automated Semi-automated Semi-automated Semi-automated	Real-time Real-time Real-time Real-time Real-time	+++ +++ +++ +++ +++								
4	Investment and human resource in PPE - Creating Value	Quantitative - Survey of projected characteristics - No names/DOB Quantitative - (Target is 5% of SDE budget) Quantitative - Contracts percentage (Target is 5% of SDE budget for PPE) Quantitative Quantitative	PPE Lead PPE Lead PPE Lead PPE Lead	Annual Annual Annual Annual	++ ++ +++ +++	++ ++ ++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	++ ++ +++ ++	+++ +++ +++ +++	++ ++ ++ ++	

Appendix 2: Examples of potential dashboard outputs created using synthetic data

Demographic Data Overview

Socio-economic overview

Appendix 4: PPIE Insights Tool Project timeline and development plan

